

Protection of Geographical Indications in Myanmar

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Abstract

A geographical indication (GI) is a sign that a product comes from a particular region which gives a special quality, reputation or other characteristic of the goods are essentially attributable to its geographical origin and human factors. The geographical indication products are needed to prevent from unauthorized used and misleading in public which can cause the damages on the consumers and producers. Geographical Indications was protected in accordance with the provisions of the conventions, treaties, agreement and law at the international level. In Myanmar, there have no special law for GI but the other statutory laws are protected on geographical indications. So, special law is needed to enact in Myanmar by exercising the compulsory registration system because to protect the interests and support the economic development of our country.

Keywords: Geographical Indications, Protection, Special Law, compulsory registration system

1. INTRODUCTION

Intellectual property is legal term that refers to creation of mind; inventions literary and artistic work. Intellectual property rights are the legally recognized exclusive rights to creation of the mind. Intellectual property is divided into two categories, industrial property and copyright. Industrial property includes patent for inventions, trademarks, industrial designs and geographical indication. Geographical indications and appellations of origin are signs used on goods that have a specific geographical origin and possess qualities, a reputation or characteristics that are essentially attributable to that place or origin. They refer to the collective right of all the producers of a given good that are located in the geographical area. Geographical indications were protected by the Paris Convention 1883, Madrid Agreement 1891, Lisbon Agreement 1958 and TRIPA Agreement. The Geographical Indications can protect the other related laws because there has no special law in our country.

1.1 Intellectual Property and Geographical Indications

Intellectual property is a collective term used to describe new ideas, inventions, design, writings, film, etc. There are protected by copyright, patents, trademarks, industrial design, etc. Those are intangible when first created, but become valuable tangible form as products.²

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² <http://www.wipo.int/ebookshop>.

Intellectual property is a commercial valuable product of human intellect, in a concrete or abstract form, such as a copyrightable work, a protectable trademark, patentable invention, protectable industrial design or a trade secret.³

Intellectual property rights are generic terms of exclusive rights given to the results gained by intellectual activities of human beings and to the sign used for business activities, and they mean important economic tools for economic, social and culture development. They give the creator the right to prevent others from making unauthorized use of their property for a limited period. It can be bought, sold, transferred need to be protected. It is an intangible right which own economic values.⁴

Intellectual property rights are like any other property right. They allow creators, inventors or owners, of patent, trademark, industrial designs or copyrighted works to benefit from their own work or investment in a creation or an invention. In addition, these rights are awarded by society to individuals or organizations principally over creative work; invention, literary and artistic works, and symbols, names, images, and designs used in commerce. They mean intangible rights which own economic values and they have some resemblance to ownership rights over physical property.⁵

Intellectual Property Rights mean the power vested by law for protecting creation of own intellectual. In that work, the copyright, the right of patent, the right of industrial design, the right of trademark, geographical indications and other types of rights are also inclusive.⁶

According to Article 27 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights;

- Everyone has the right freely to participate in the cultural life of the community, to enjoy the arts and to share in scientific advancement and its benefits, and
- Everyone has the right to the protection of the moral and material interests resulting from any scientific, literary or artistic production of which he is the author.

Geographical indications (GIs) are signs which identify goods that are originating from a specific place and possess a given quality, reputation or other characteristic that is essentially attributable to that geographical origin. GIs enable consumers to differentiate products, as they pay increasing attention to the geographical origin of products. One of the key benefits of GIs for consumers is therefore to guarantee the quality of the product.⁷

The fundamental condition is that the quality, the reputation or other characteristics of the product are linked to its geographical origin, by virtue of climate, know-how or another kind of knowledge deeply rooted in that area. “Colombian coffee” for instance is a GI as the name of the country refers to the origin and quality of the product. The mountains where

³ Bryan A Garner, Black's law Dictionary, 7 Edition, 1999 P-649.

⁴ <http://www.wipo.int/ebookshop>.

⁵ Law journal, Volume VII, serial No-2, 2006, P-164.

⁶ Section-2(8) of the Myanmar Copyright Law, 2019

⁷ A Booklet on ASEAN Geographical Indications Procedure, P-8.

coffee tree grow, the selection of the coffee variety and the harvest and transformation process are the elements conferring the product its unique characteristics.⁸

Geographical indications are protected in accordance with national law and under a wide range of concept, such as against unfair competition, consumer protection laws, law for the protection of geographical indications or appellations of origin. In essence, unauthorized parties may not use geographical indications if such use is likely to mislead the public as to the origin of the product. Sanctions may range from court injunctions preventing the further unauthorized use of the geographical indication, to the payment of damages and fines or serious, even imprisonment.⁹

An appellation of origin is a special kind of geographical indication. It generally consists of a geographical name or traditional designation used on products which have a specific quality or characteristic that area essentially due to the geographical environment in which they are produced.¹⁰

Registration is one of the important protection systems of geographical indication product. Sometime it can be registered as trademark, collective marks and certification marks. Once a geographical indication has been registered as a collective mark, the association that owns it has the right to prohibit its use by persons who are not member of association.¹¹

Once registered on the International Register, the appellation of origin is valid and effective as long as the appellation remains protected in the country origin. No renewal is necessary and once protected, the appellation of origin is prevented from appellation of origin must be first protected in its country origin.

The Intellectual Register set up under the Lisbon System is maintained by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO). Applications for registration must be filed with WIPO y the competent authority of the country of origin and in this way, any local producers desiring a registration of an appellation of origin must first satisfy the requirement of the country of origin.

Upon registration on the International Register, WIPO then notifies the registration to the national authorities of the Lisbon Union. The competent national authorities within the Lisbon Union have a right, within a period of one year form the date of receipt of the notification, to issue a refusal of protection in relation to the appellation of origin concerned stating the grounds of the refusal.

Once notified of the declaration of refusal, the interested party may avail himself of all the judicial and administrative remedies open to national of the country which has refused the protection. If no declaration of refusal is received within the relevant time limit , the

⁸ [https:// www.origin-gi.com/web-article](https://www.origin-gi.com/web-article).

⁹ International Trade Center, World Intellectual Property Organization, Marketing Crafts and Visual Arts; The Role of Intellectual Property,2003,p.87.

¹⁰ <http://www.wipo.int>.

¹¹ WIPO, Intellectual Property Handbook, 2ndedition, 2004, p.123

protection of the appellation of origin takes effect in that country from the date of international registration.¹²

Intellectual property comes from the human intellect such as patent, copyright and trademark. These are the creation of human mind which can protect by owners, creators and inventors according to the intellectual property rights. Geographical indications were also included in the intellectual property. Therefore, geographical indications were protected by applying the registration system at the national and international level in accord with the provisions of the Conventions, agreements and laws.

2. INTERNATIONAL ENGAGEMENT FOR THE PROTECTION GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS

At the International Level, protection of Geographical Indication is developed through the international instruments, the most related International Conventions are-

- (i) Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property (1883)
- (ii) Madrid Agreement for the Repression of False or Deceptive Indications of Sources of Goods (1891)
- (iii) Lisbon Agreement for the Protection of Application of Origin and Their International Registration (1958)
- (iv) Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights (TRIPS) 1994.

Paris Convention for the protection of Industrial Property was held of March 20, 1883, as revised, at Brussels on December 14, 1900, at Washington on June 2, 1911, at the Hague on November 6, 1925, at Lisbon on October 31, 1958, and at Stockholm on July 14, 1967 and as amended on September 28, 1979. Paris Convention's now has 176 total contracting member countries. Which makes it one of the most widely adopted treaties worldwide The Paris Convention was the first multilateral agreement to cover geographical indications.

The Paris Convention sets forth that, in cases of "direct or indirect use of a false indication of the source of the goods or the identity of the producer, manufacturer or merchant."¹³

It provides that goods bearing a false indication of source are subject to seizure upon importation into countries party to the Paris Convention, or within the country where the unlawful affixation of the indication of source occurred or within the country of importation. Seizure shall take place at the request of the public prosecutor, or any other competent authority, or any interested party and countries party to the Paris Convention whose national laws do not permit seizure on importation or inside the country to replace those remedies by either a prohibition of importation or by any other nationally available remedy.¹⁴

¹² Susanna H S Leong, Intellectual Property Law of Singapore, 2013, p-1025.

¹³ Article 10 of the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, 1883. .

¹⁴ Article 9 Ibid.

Therefore, under the Paris Convention for the protection of geographical indication, there must to seize all goods bearing false or misleading indication when the goods are imported into member countries.

The Madrid Agreement for the Repression of False or Deceptive Indications of Source on Goods was originally drafted in 1891 and revised in 1911 and 1934. Agreement aims at the repression not only of false, but also of deceptive, indications of source.

According to Madrid Agreement, all goods bearing a false or deceptive indication by which one of the countries to which this Agreement applies, or a place situated therein, is directly or indirectly indicated as being the country or place of origin shall be seized on importation into any of the said countries. Seizure shall also be effected in the country where the false or deceptive indication of source has been applied, or into which the goods bearing the false or deceptive indication have been imported.¹⁵

The countries to which this agreement applies also undertake to prohibit the use, in connection with the sale or display or offering for sale of any goods, of all indication in the nature of publicity capable of deceiving the public as to the source of goods, and appearing on signs, advertisements, invoices, wine lists, business letters or papers, or any other commercial communication.¹⁶

Lisbon Agreement for the protection of applications of origin and their international registration includes Articles 1 to 11.

In Article 1(2) of the Lisbon Agreement states that the countries to the Lisbon Agreement undertake to protect on their territories, in accordance with the terms of this Agreement, the appellations of origin of products of the other countries of the Special Union, recognized and protected as such in the country of origin and registered at the International Bureau of Intellectual Property referred to in the Convention establishing the World Intellectual Property Organization.¹⁷

In Article 2(1) of the Lisbon Agreement provides that the protection of applications of origin, that is the "geographical denomination of a country, region, or locality, which serves to designate a product originating therein, the quality or characteristics of which are due exclusively or essentially to the geographical environment, including natural and human factors."¹⁸

Therefore, in order to be protected under the Lisbon Agreement, the appellation of origin to fulfill two conditions. The first condition is that the appellation of origin must be recognized and protected as such in the country of origin. Second condition is that the appellation of origin must be registered with the international Bureau of WIPO.¹⁹

¹⁵ Article 1(1) of the Madrid Agreement for the Repression of False and Deceptive Indication of Sources of Goods, 1891.

¹⁶ Article 3 bis, Ibid.

¹⁷ Article 1(2) of the Lisbon Agreement for the Protection of Application of Origin and their International Registration, 1958.

¹⁸ Article 2(1) Ibid.

¹⁹ WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook; Policy, Law and Use, 2nd edition, 2004, P.127.

The Agreement on Trade-Related Aspects of Intellectual Property Rights 1994 is the basic instrument for protection of industrial property rights. It contains a special section dedicated to geographical indications Section 3 of Part II.

In respect of geographical indications, Members shall provide the legal means for interested parties to prevent:

- (a) The use of any means in the designation or presentation of a good that indicates or suggests that the good in question originates in a geographical area other than the true place of the origin in a manner which misleads the public as to the geographical origin of the good;
- (b) Any use which constitutes an act of unfair competition within the meaning of Article 10 bis of the Paris Convention (1967).²⁰

TRIPS Agreement deals specifically with the registration of trademarks containing or consisting of a geographical indication, for goods not originating in the territory indicated, if the use of those trademarks for such goods would be misleading as to the true place of origin of the goods. The remedy that must be available in that situation is refusal or invalidation of the trademark registration, either ex officio, if the applicable law allows, or at the request of an interested party.²¹

All governments must provide the owners of the GI the right, under their laws, to prevent the use of a geographical indication. This applies even where the public is not being misled, where there is no unfair competition and where the true origin of the good is indicated or the geographical indication is accompanied by expressions such as “kind”, “type”, “style”, “imitation” or the like. Similar protection must be given to geographical indications identifying spirits.²²

Thailand experienced the first case of biopiracy when a newly developed hybrid variety under the name “Jasmati” was registered in 1997 by the Rice Tec Corporation at the Patent and Trademark Office of the United States of America. The name contains two variants of two rice varieties: jasmine rice from Thailand and basmati rice from the Indian subcontinent. However, “Jasmati” rice, which is a hybridized variety called Della that was developed from the Italian Bertone rice in the United States, has characteristics other than those of basmati and jasmine rice. The use of the name Jasmati could therefore mislead rice consumers by making them wrongly believe that Jasmati rice would have the same characteristics as jasmine rice from Thailand and/or basmati rice from the Indian subcontinent, even though the rice was not genetically related to the jasmine rice grown in Thailand. This concern was reinforced by the finding of a market survey showing that over half of the consumers in the United States buying “Jasmati” thought it was related to jasmine and basmati rice (Roggemann, 2005).

The importance of rice for Thailand derives not only from its being a major staple food for domestic consumption but also from its export volume and value. Thailand has been one of the world’s largest rice exporters for nearly three decades (Toriyama, Heong and

²⁰ Article 22 (2) of the TRIPS Agreement, 1994.

²¹ Article 22 (3) Ibid.

²² Article 23 of the TRIPS Agreement, 1994.

Hardy, 2005). Its market share amounted to more than 25 per cent of the global total traded between 2005 and 2010, leaving the second and third largest exporters, Viet Nam and Pakistan, far behind (see figure 1). Exporting rice to the global market has resulted in considerable export revenues not only for Thailand as a whole but also for individual rice farmers.

Hence, concerns are related to the economic importance of Thai jasmine rice, which is one of Thailand's most important agricultural export crops and which is regarded as a source of culture and belief. Against this backdrop, the Act on GI Protection B.E. 2546 was introduced in 2003 as a tool for protecting origin-based products from biopiracy (Jaovisidha, 2003), and in the case of jasmine rice, the registration of a rice patent on its aroma genes in the United States in 2008. In addition, to promote the cultivation and marketing of jasmine rice, the Thai Hom Mali Rice Trade Association Thung Kula Rong-Hai Geographical Indication was established in 2008. By 2008/09, there were 1,131 Thai jasmine rice farmers, 13 exporters and 4 processors certified as GI operators for Thung Kula Rong-Hai rice by the Department of Intellectual Property (Ngokkuen and Grote, 2011; 2012).²³

Therefore, the Paris Convention and Madrid Agreement for the protection of geographical indications must seize all good bearing false or misleading indications in accordance with the provision of this convention.

Lisbon Agreement for the protection of an appellation of origin registered to national legislation. In addition to any sanctions applicable pursuant to the Paris Convention and the Madrid Agreement, all the sanctions provided for in national legislation, whether civil, penal or administrative, are to be applied.

The TRIPS Agreement permits Members to protect the Geographical Indication of goods where the quality, reputation or other characteristic of goods are attributable to their geographical origin.

3. PROTECTION FOR GEOGRAPHICAL INDICATIONS IN MYANMAR

In Myanmar, there is no specific statutory Law to protect Geographical Indications. The offender was intended to deceive or cause confusion among the general public as to the condition and originality of goods is deemed to be an offense under the Myanmar Merchandise Mark Act, 1889, Specific Relief Act, 1877, Trademark Law 2019 and Competitions Law 1889.

According to section 37(b) of the Constitution of the Republic of the Union of Myanmar, 2008, the Union shall enact necessary law to supervise extraction and utilization of State-owned natural resources by economic forces.

No businessman shall carry out any of the following acts which mislead the consumers:

²³ <https://www.unescap.org/sites/default/files/chap-5-Ngokkuen.pdf>.

- (a) Carrying out with intention to compete with the use of deceptive information which misleads the legally registered name of goods, business slogan, logo, packaging, geographical indication and other elements.
- (b) Carrying out business such as production of good and services by using the information contained in sub section (a).²⁴

Any person who violates the prohibitions contained in Section 18 shall, on conviction, be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding one year or with fine not exceeding Kyat fifty Lakhs or both.²⁵

In the area of registration procedures, any legal entity representing the following persons of the locality in which the relevant goods is produced, desirous of registration of a geographical indication shall apply to the Registrar for registration in conformity with the stipulations;

- (a) Persons who produce goods of natural products or natural resources;
 - (b) Producers of agricultural products;
 - (c) Producers who make handicraft or industrial products; or
 - (d) On behalf of the persons under sub-section (a) to (c), authorities of the relative government department, government organizations."²⁶
- The application should be accompanied by the following:
- (i) a specification describing in sufficient details the specific characteristics or quality or reputation of the goods;
 - (ii) the link between a specific quality, the reputation or the characteristics of goods, geographical origin and method of production;
 - (iii) Other prescribed particulars.²⁷

The applicants shall pay the registration fee when submitting their application. A geographical indication that involves any of the following points shall not be entitled for registration:

- (a) Not complying with the definition of geographical indication in section 2 sub-section (o);
- (b) Being a generic term or customary in common language of the good that are to use such geographical indication in the Union.
- (c) Being a geographical indication which is contrary to public order or good morals or public policy.²⁸
- (d) Only producers carrying on their activities in the geographical area specified in the register shall have the right to use a registered geographical indication, in the course of trade, with respect to the products specified in the register.

²⁴ Section 18 of the Competition Law, Myanmar 2015.

²⁵ Section 42, Ibid.

²⁶ Section 53 of the Trademark Law, Myanmar 2019.

²⁷ Section 54(b) Ibid.

²⁸ Section 56 Ibid.

Provided that such products possess the quality, reputation or other characteristics specified in the register.

- (e) In the case of homonymous geographical indications, protection shall be accorded to each indication, provided that the practical conditions under which the homonymous indications will be differentiated from each other, taking into account the need to ensure equitable treatment of the producers concerned and that consumers are not misled.
- (f) The right holder of the registered geographical indication shall have the rights to prevent the following matters:
 - (i) the use of any means in the presentation of the goods to be originated in a geographical area other than the true place of origin in a manner which misleads the public as to the geographical indication of the goods;
 - (ii) any use of a registered geographical indication which constitutes an act of unfair competition;
 - (iii) any use of a geographical indication identifying goods not originating in the place indicated by the geographical indication in question, even where the true origin of the goods is indicated or the geographical indication is used in translation or accompanied by expressions such as "kind", "type", "style", "imitation" or the same.
- (g) The rights under subsections (a) and (c) do not apply to another geographical indication which, although literally true as to the territory, region or locality in which the goods originate, falsely represents to the public that the goods originate in another territory.²⁹

The term of the protection of a geographical indication shall be valid from the filing date of the application under this Law as long as the product specifications compliance with such as quality, characteristic and reputation are reputation are longer ensured.³⁰

- (h) Whoever commits any of the following acts on the commercial purposes without the consent of the right holder shall, on conviction, be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding three years or with a fine not exceeding five million kyats, or with both:
 - (i) Counterfeiting a mark;
 - (ii) Applying a counterfeit mark to goods or using it in connection with services;
 - (iii) Possessing any materials or implements, the predominant use of which is likely to be to counterfeit a mark or applying a counterfeit mark to goods.
- (i) Whoever commits any of the following acts on the commercial purposes shall, on conviction, be punished with imprisonment for a term not exceeding two years or with a fine not exceeding five million kyats, or with both:

²⁹ Section 57 of the Trademark Law, Myanmar 2019.

³⁰ Section 59, Ibid.

- (i) Dealing or possessing in counterfeit mark goods;
- (ii) Importing into or exporting from the State, counterfeit mark goods.³¹

Therefore, if one of the persons commits the infringement and counterfeit on GI products can be punished in accord with the provisions of the other related laws in Myanmar.

In Myanmar, there have seven item products of GI such as Paw San Hmwey rice from Shwebo, tea leaf, Bagn Lacquare ware, Pa Thein umbrella, coffee seeds from Ywa Ngan, louts fiber from Inlay and Sein Ta Lone mango Kyaukse for having the right to use a registered Geographical Indication in the course of trade.

4. SUGGESTIONS

In Myanmar, there is no special law to protect geographical indications. This is the lack of our country to support effectively on the geographical indication's products. And then, people of legal awareness concerned with geographical indications are very vague, even today. Moreover, consumers do not complain to the relevant government and there are no effective sanctions on the infringements which are not only in the area of geographical origins, but in general. This is the lack of cooperation between the public and government organizations. Therefore, the relevant government department was needed to create the awareness programs and technical assistance for the public which can cause the effective encouragement. And then, we should apply the compulsory registration system by providing details on the registration procedures and process. It will support not only to reduce unauthorized use but also to develop the economic sector.

5. CONCLUSION

Geographical indication is an important method of indicating the origin of goods and services. GI products can promote commerce by informing the customer of the origin of the products. In the promotion of the commerce the registration plays an important role for producers because only the registrar can protect the false or misuse and infringement of Geographical Indications' products from unauthorized producers. And then, registration is a protection system of Geographical Indications which can get more reputation for added values to a product. Protection of geographical indication is a national basic but there are various international treaties that assist the protection in a range of countries. Myanmar has no specific law for geographical indications. But some existing laws are protected on false use or misuse and infringement on geographical indications. It is an important issue to enact the special law for geographical indications because of the many of the GI products of Myanmar. It should exercise the compulsory registration system to promote the economic development and reputations of our country. It will need to educate and awareness to understand about GI among the local producers and community. It is also need to cooperate and coordinate with local and international organizations to promote the reputation and enter into the international market of the GI products.

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³¹ Section 87, Ibid.

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